

Language, Society, and Cultural Differences in *Representation: The Strange Case of Malangese Boso Walikan*

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Abstract: This paper offers a critical response to fundamental theories of representation in the introductory section of *Representation: Cultural Representations and Signifying Practices*, a book written by Hall, Evans, and Nixon. As of January 2023, the book had won critical acclaim and was cited 13,500 times. The writers discuss how important a system of representation operates to connect language, society, and cultural differences in Malang, East Java, Indonesia. Using a specific case of *Boso Walikan*, the Malangese slang language as a representational system, the writers discover that cultural differences may occur within the same society where most people share the same cultural values and speak the same language. In this case, not all Malangese people like to speak their unique slang language although they were born and have grown up in Malang and can speak the slang well. In the end, the whole process of strange to familiar ideas of expressions, thus representations, matches very closely with the concept of shared meaning in any given culture or unique system of representation. For the case of *Boso Walikan*, it seems safe to suggest that any of its native users are just ‘more experienced’ speakers of the slang language.

Keywords: *boso walikan*, meaning, representation, signifying practice

Introduction

Representation: Cultural Representations and Signifying Practices is a seminal book written by Hall, Evans, and Nixon (2013). As of January 2023, the book has been influential and cited 13,500 times. The textbook is currently a recommended

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book in some courses of linguistics, humanities, and cultural studies at Australian universities (Masjhadi, 2018). The book offers an essential source for teachers and learners who are interested in studying and doing research in cultural and media studies. Since its first publication in 1997, the book has provided practical assistance for students learning the instruments to question and analyse public texts and images critically (Sage, 2022).

In their introduction to the book, Hall, Evans, and Nixon (2013) describe the connection between language, society, and cultural differences. Unlike their fellow linguists, they focus their argumentative ideas on two powerful phrases: “shared meanings” and “representational system”. They simplify the definition of culture by saying that “culture is about shared meanings” (p.1). They further assert that meaning is produced and exchanged in language and language works as a system of representation.

Hall et al. (2013) claim that language “operates as a representational system” (p.1). By this they mean to pinpoint that when we speak to other people, we employ signs and symbols to represent our concepts, ideas, and feelings. Those signs and symbols can be in the form of sounds, words, images, notes, or objects. The Indonesian word *bambu runcing* (a bamboo pole with a sharpened tip), for example, can be interpreted differently by speakers of the Indonesian language. Firstly, it connotes the bravery, determination and relentless struggle of Indonesian warriors who fought for independence. During the revolutionary war against the Dutch when most Indonesian combatants were deprived of modern weaponry, their military leaders frequently said that when guns or rifles were hard to find, a courageous soldier could use a *bambu runcing* to kill a Dutch soldier. Secondly, *bambu runcing* symbolises resourcefulness. Indonesian villagers have found many uses for sharpened bamboo poles: they can be utilised as a very practical tool to place seeds on a paddy field, they can be used to prod coconut clusters during harvest time, and they can turn into makeshift spatula to fry certain herbs. Here, we know that the term *bambu runcing* signifies something. It has two meanings depending on how people interpret or represent it. This suits Hall’s statement that “In any culture, there is always a great diversity of meanings about any topic, and more than one way of interpreting or representing it” (p.2).

Language, Society, and Cultural Differences

In establishing a connection between language, society, and cultural differences, Hall et al. (2013) support their argument by saying that culture is referred to as “whatever is distinctive about the ‘way of life’ of a people, community, nation, or social group” (p.2). For instance, touching someone else’s head is a cultural

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practice that can be interpreted differently by Indonesian and English people. In Indonesian culture touching someone else's head is considered taboo. Some people, especially Javanese, can get offended if someone touches their head. This is because they interpret touching someone else's head as a sign of contempt or humiliation. In England, on the other hand, people sometimes touch other people's heads. English footballers, for example, will enthusiastically pat their teammates' heads after the latter score a goal. Nobody will get offended because the footballers and spectators understand that touching someone else's head means appreciating someone else's achievement. The two cultural differences clearly show that culture works through a representational system in which meaning plays an important role.

Upon analysing the two examples above, we further believe that there will be no serious cultural problem for people who live in the same culture since they “share sets of concepts, images and ideas which enable them to think and feel about the world, and thus to interpret the world roughly in the same ways” (p.6). Indonesian and English people, who belong to their respective communities, share cultural values through their own system of representation. Here, society is a place in which language and culture are produced through a system of representation. This makes sense because language can give “one general model of how culture and representation work” (p.6) and works as “a representational system” (p.1).

Hall et al. (2013) further elaborate the significant role of society related to discourses when differentiating between *semiotic* and *discursive* approaches (p.6). The *semiotic* approach has its emphasis on “how language produces meaning” (its poetics), while the *discursive* approach deals with “the *effects and consequences* of representation” (its politics) (p.6). Using the second approach, Hall shows the importance of society by saying that discourses are “a cluster (or formation) of ideas, images, and practices, which provide ways of talking about, forms of knowledge and conduct associated with, a particular topic, social activity or institutional site in society” (p.6). It should be noted that in any society, language can be a problem involving personality and social problems (e.g., split identity and low self-esteem) and political problems (e.g., regional conflicts and national disunity) (Baker & Wright, 2017; Masduqi, 2010; Masduqi & Subiyanto, 2020). Therefore, people should be sensible and tolerant whenever they grapple with the delicate issues of language, society, and cultural differences.

The Slang Language in Malang

The way Hall et al. (2013) describe the representational system in connecting language, society, and cultural differences can be useful to interpret an embarrassing incident we experienced last year. For decades we have lived and worked in Malang,

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the second biggest city in East Java province of Indonesia, where the people are famous for their unique slang language, *Boso Walikan*. *Boso Walikan* is actually far from complicated. It is a flexible combination between Javanese and Indonesian languages that are spoken in backward formations (Hermawan, 2014; Hoogervorst, 2014; Rozin et al., 2022; Tropea, 2022; Yannuar, 2022). For example, instead of saying *kaos kamu apik* (your shirt is nice – in a normal sentence formation), Malangese may opt to say *soak umak kipa* (your shirt is nice – in a backward sentence formation). Indonesian people coming from other provinces, often find this simple practice of reversing words quite baffling. They may identify and understand that *soak umak* is a backward formation from *kaos kamu* because the phrase is taken from the Indonesian language. However, they will get confused when the backward phrase is ended with the addition of the word *apik*. This is because they do not know that the term *apik* (nice) is taken from the Javanese language.

One day we went to Malang Central Market to buy T-shirts. In our attempt to haggle for lower price, we usually speak in Malangese slang to the shopkeeper. This strategy worked well in our previous contact with a shop attendant. When we entered a T-shirt stall in the market, one of us (the first writer of this paper) asked an old shop assistant, “*Pak, soak ireng iki orip?*” (Sir, how much is the black T-shirt? – the normal sentence formation should be *Pak, kaos ireng iki piro?*). At first, he refused to answer. When the same question was repeated, he snapped, “*Kaos iku sewidak ewu!*” (That would be IDR 60,000.00 – or about \$5). We were taken aback for two reasons. First, the shop assistant did not answer the question using Malangese slang expression. Secondly, the tone of his speech hinted indignation, as if he tried to show his seething anger. Later, when we were about to leave the shop, the female cashier whispered to us that we should not have spoken the Malangese slang expression because the old shop assistant adored politeness and it was obvious that he considered the use Malangese slang as something impolite.

Another incident that involved discursive practice in language regarding *Boso Walikan* occurred to the researchers in the past. Back when we were university students, we met many new friends who were not native Malangese. For the sake of simplicity, those then ‘outsiders’ were having some problems in communicating their ideas as some of them were only beginning to get exposed to *Boso Walikan* in their life. Not surprisingly, these outsiders were left feeling ‘unattached’ or as if they were not part of the same group despite the fact, they were already members of that group.

At this point, these outsiders were experiencing what Hall et al. (2013) point out as the effect and consequences of representation as they understood the system’s politics, discursively though not necessarily by practice, that is, their position as ‘aliens’ to the group due to their inability to speak the same language. The next logical step for them was then to immediately create practical strategies to enable them to

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feel that they really belonged to the group. This craving for acknowledgement is also an example of politics of representation since the initiation, i.e., the process that leads these strangers to be (to feel) accepted in the group, can only be through language, specifically speaking the same language.

What happened next was that many of these outsiders tried to cope with, copy, learn and practise the very language of *Boso Walikan* through learning by doing and or first-hand trial and error. One of the most interesting strategies was that many of them tended to reverse all words, any words sometimes, even though these vocabularies were difficult or even unheard of by the native speakers of Malangese *Boso Walikan*. This phenomenon created quite a funny scene as the unfamiliar expressions were confusing, not only by their nature, but also their effect on both the speakers and the listeners.

One of these expressions were regular sentences meant to ask questions about something such as, “*Rek, ketok celono sing tak pepe ndek kene ta?*” (Guys, have you seen any pairs of trousers I dried off around here?). For this common way of asking simple things, most native users will come up with something like “*Ker, ketok celono sing tak pepe ndek kene ta?*”, that is, they would refrain from reversing anything except the already regular name-calling of “*Rek*” into “*Ker*” as most natives also ‘naturally’ understand there is no point in using *Boso Walikan* unless they usually want to say something with a more unique kind of intention.

For many of the outsiders, the desire to be immediately acknowledged as ones of the ‘insiders’ (that is, those who grew up natively with *Boso Walikan* as unique identity) was proven to be stronger as they, then, tended to create very strange expressions like “*Ker, kotek onolek ngis tak epep ndek enek ta?*” Despite the fact that such expression does reflect these outsiders’ serious effort to be quickly appreciated as one of the insiders, yet for most of the native users of *Boso Walikan* themselves, terms as “*kotek*” as inversion of “*ketok*”, or “*onolek*” (the Indonesian phoneme /c/ and /k/ tend to merge when used as end-sound of words) as the inversion of “*celono*”, and “*epep*” as a result of reversing “*pepe*” not only do sound unfamiliar, but also somewhat far-fetched as these terms or vocabularies were rarely to be reversed naturally as they were used in daily conversations. A plausible explanation to this would be that most native users of *Boso Walikan* who grew up with the system might already be ‘at home’ with the system and refrain themselves from using anything other than those that are already given or shared beforehand in the discourse.

In order to clarify the case further, this is just another example of common question that those outsiders often used ‘mis-appropriately’ in a casual conversation: “*Lo, awakmu sido budal jam piro?*” (So, at what time do you actually plan to go?). To first make a comparison, most native users will likely go with something like “*Lo, awakmu sido ladup jam orip?*”. Again, this kind of expression seems to be naturally

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used to maintain being as effective as possible while still being unique in their way of practising culture. On the contrary, most of Boso Walikan's new users would create anything that sounded such as “*Lo, umkawa odis ladup mak orip?*”

It is noticeable by most native users that expressions such as “umkawa” to replace “awakmu” and “mak” to replace “jam” (because of the difficulty of pronouncing Indonesian phoneme /j/ at the end of word thus it usually blends more with Indonesian /k/) are considered strange and, admittedly, rather funny. Yet, all these examples are nothing but evidence for how eager any of those outsiders to be (feel) welcomed by being an actual part of the group, rather than unattached members of that very group.

Other than just being funny or strange, the outsiders' effort in creating such expressions does function accordingly in the politics of representations as Hall et al. (2013) suggests. At first, this seemingly funny or innocent process of reversing any words using *Boso Walikan* only made nothing but awkward yet regular and noticeable slight pauses between utterances or sentences. These occurring halts might be due to the time these outsiders need to think or take in order to contemplate on the spot or to speak on the go while imagining how these words should be said in their unnatural order of reversal. At this point as well, these regular stops seemed to have caused no damages except to lead to minor confusions as the native users were also forced, in return, to think or contemplate what these outsiders meant with their sayings.

What happened next was nothing sort of funny as many of these native users even started to internalise those strange expressions, whether they were aware of such a process. Thus, as time went by, it was not uncommon that many of these funny and unnatural *Boso Walikan*'s terms grew into more and more common practical ways of saying things as the vocabularies continued to be used time and again; part of it might be due to the native speakers' desperate attempts to deliver their ideas quicker or more effectively to these outsiders.

The above happening gives a clear picture that what Hall, et al. (2013) propose as the effects and consequences of representation is also a non-linear term, instead of a singular or one-way direction in which only one part of cultural agents or members will take the risks while others continue managing to avoid such consequences. The internalisation processes the native users of *Boso Walikan* were going through may prove that language, as a practical representation of culture, is a reciprocal and welcoming process of exchanging ideas. It is a dual practice as the native users as the first initiators of new meanings were eventually also forced to accept new suggestions beyond their language domain. It is, at the same time, welcoming because in the process of establishing the network of meaning, *Boso Walikan* itself, as one of cultural systems of representations, seems to allow these so-

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called outsiders to actually come up and invent new phrases previously unfamiliar even to the system itself.

Concluding Remarks

The incidents narrated above shows how important a system of representation operates to connect between language, society, and cultural difference. We begin to realise that by using the Malangese slang language as a representational system, we possibly discover that a cultural difference may occur within the same society where most people share the same cultural values and speak the same language. In this case, not all Malangese people like to speak their own unique slang language although they were born and grown up in Malang and can speak the slang language well. Furthermore, as Hall et al. (2013) suggest, meaning plays a vital role in the central issue of the system of representation. It is never finally fixed as “there are always different circuits of meaning circulating in any culture at the same time, overlapping discursive formations, from which we draw to create meaning or to express what we think” (p.10).

In the end, the whole process of strange to familiar ideas of expressions, thus representations, matches very closely with the concept of shared meaning in any given culture or unique system of representation. For the case of *Boso Walikan*, it seems safe to suggest that any of its native users are just ‘more experienced’ speakers of the said language. It is true that these fellows are first to be exposed of and in turn to exploit *Boso Walikan* to make it part of their unique cultural identity or way of sharing ideas. Yet, none of this simply means, or necessarily means to say that these native users are also the owner of the system.

The reference of different circuits of meaning that allow many of cultural agents to express their ideas seems to be evidence by itself as even the native users, like it or not, are forced to acknowledge any kind of unfamiliarity and strangeness so that ideas can be represented and understood together and in case of par excellence, the newcomers are given access, hence power, to create anything new that the system may later use and claim as their own.

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